

Promotion of Water Reuse Applications: Development of a DST to Facilitate the Selection of the Best Purification Treatment

I. Salmerón^{a,b}, S. Venditti^b, P. Núñez-Tafalla^b, M. Biehler^a, J. Hansen^b.

^aTR-Engineering, 86-88 Rue de l'Égalité, L-1456 Luxembourg
(E-mail: i.salmeron@tr-engineering.lu, m.biehler@tr-engineering.lu)

^bUniversity of Luxembourg, Department of Engineering, 6, rue Richard Coudenhove-Kalergi, L-1359 Luxembourg
(E-mail: silvia.venditti@uni.lu, paula.nunez@uni.lu, joachim.hansen@uni.lu)

Abstract

Limited water availability is a problem of high concern that could lead to severe social and economic crises. To mitigate it, alternative water sources like stormwater, rainwater, greywater, and wastewater effluents offer promising solutions for non-potable uses such as irrigation or service water. However, ensuring the safe reuse of these resources requires compliance with the emerging regulations and guidelines, such as the European Regulation 2020/741, which set strict quality standards. Purification technologies, including UV radiation, adsorption, natural based solutions or advanced oxidation processes are very powerful treatments able to achieve the required quality but it is necessary to explore their combination to find a suitable solution. The LëtZREUSE project aims to develop an innovative decision-support tool (DST) capable of aiding in the selection of the most appropriate technology (or combination) for each situation in a fast and effective way. The DST integrates (a) water characteristics, (b) the new regulatory requirements (c) micropollutants and pathogens as quality standards, d) technological effectiveness as well as e) final user preferences and f) applications to recommend the most suitable treatment methods. The DST development will be based on experiences with real waters from different sources in Luxembourg. The collaboration between the University of Luxembourg and TR-Engineering for this project will allow to evaluate other economical and practical aspects, as well as the user's needs.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Bacteria, Microcontaminants, Reclaimed water, Water purification

INTRODUCTION

The limited water availability has been reported since years by international organizations as a problem that may cause severe social and economic crises in a near future. To mitigate this, it is becoming increasingly necessary to look for alternative sources of water, which can meet the current demand without losing quality of service. Effluent from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) is a resource that is always available in large amounts, so its reuse for irrigation can lead to a very significant reduction in the demand for drinking water. However, it is important to note that stormwater, rainwater and even greywater can also be a valuable resource to satisfy the non-potable applications as service water or for groundwater replenishment.

Legislation is being developed at different levels to provide a framework for water reuse, depending on its final use. For example, European Regulation 2020/741 establishes the quality parameters for water reuse in agriculture. At national level, as an example, in October 2024, Spain has published its new Water Reuse Regulation (Real Decreto 1085/2024) which cover other applications such as artificial recharge of aquifers and recreational uses. Other countries, such as Luxembourg, are currently also working on their own legislation for the use of reclaimed water as service water.

Achieving the quality objectives outlined in current regulations ensuring a safe reuse needs the implementation of advanced technologies capable of eliminating pollutants, including organic compounds of anthropogenic origin, and microorganisms. Among those purification methods – used stand-alone or in combination - are oxidative processes, physical separation (membrane and adsorption) nature-based solutions and hybrid systems, which have been deeply studied in literature with very promising results. Nevertheless, the final performance of each method depends very

much on the characteristics of the untreated water itself. Therefore, a detailed assessment of water crucial parameters, corresponding regulations, and quality standards is required for the choice of the best treatment alternative.

In literature many different decision-support tools (DSTs) have been previously developed to help in the decision-making process when selecting a water treatment to be implemented. Nonetheless, most available tools are outdated and are only able to tailor organic matter and nutrients but not pesticides, drugs, personal care products or microorganisms as required by the current legislation.

In this context the LëtZREUSE project arises, aiming to address these challenges by developing an innovative DST coherent with the contemporary requirements. The proposed DST, is conceived with a wide view, implementing the following aspects as decision criteria: 1) Type of water to be reuse and their physical-chemical characteristics, 2) International and national regulations and guidelines to be applied, 3) Quality requirements in terms of nutrients, micropollutants and pathogens to be accomplished, 4) Requirements and preferences of the final user of the reclaimed water, 5) Evaluation of the purification efficiency of the technologies and 6) The final purpose of the water. This is only possible thanks to the collaboration of TR-Engineering - an engineering office with an extensive expertise in hydraulic engineering in Luxembourg - and the University of Luxembourg, as well as the contributions of the WWTP operators the Water Management Authority and the Ministry of the Environment, Climate and Biodiversity of Luxembourg.

The DST will be then appropriate for its application to Luxembourg but also for other regions, being able to provide the most suitable solution avoiding reducing the time and cost associate to perform a detailed case of study. Luxembourg has already initiated a strategy to mitigate the discharge of organic trace substances (micropollutants (MPs)) into water bodies by upgrading existing WWTPs with a quaternary treatment applying advanced technologies. The initial plan included the upgrade of 14 WWTPs, and other WWTPs can be added based on risk assessment criteria. This context is the perfect framework for the proposed DST, that can additionally propose solutions to achieve the disinfection target for a safe reuse of the reclaimed wastewater.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The LëtZREUSE project is divided into two differentiated phases with two key objectives:

1. Identification and evaluation of the available technologies for water purification. A bibliographic study has been carried out to find the recommended treatments for each type of water according to the most recent technological advances. The current applicable regulations were also identified, which established the required quality parameters to be reached. The proposed technologies have been studied in a real scenario to determine their efficiency.

2. Development of the DST. The results obtained in the previous phase are processed and analysed as a basis for the generation of a DST-software that will help in the fast and effective selection of the best purification treatment for each type of water and concrete situation, avoiding time-consuming and resource-consuming case studies.

Experimental set-up

UV disinfection. The system consisted of a 40W nominal power low-pressure lamp (UV-C, 2 irradiation peaks: 185nm and 254 nm) from Enviolet GmbH ((Fig. 1a) connected to a recirculation tank and feed by a centrifugal pump at 800L/h. The volume treated was 30L, operating in batch mode.

Adsorption. A plexiglass column (Europlex) of 4 cm of internal diameter and 1 m of height was filled with a 10 cm of gravel for drainage and 75cm of commercial granular activated carbon (GAC), CarboTech DGF 8x30 GL provided by CarboTech (Fig. 1b). The GAC column was feed with the water to be treated at a flow rate of 28 mL/min, meaning approximately 30 minutes of contact time.

Constructed wetlands (CW) at mesocosm scale. The set-up was composed of two tanks of 20.25 L of volume and 675cm² of surface each (Fig. 1c). They were filled from the bottom to the top with a 10 cm of a drainage layer of gravel and a 20 cm layer of a mixed substrate of 5% biologically activated biochar and 95% sand. Both units were planted with *Phragmites australis* and *Iris Pseudacorus*. They were watered twice per day during 30 min with two peristaltic pumps (Watson Marlow, UK) at a flow rate of 130 ml/min, resulting in a Hydraulic Loading Rate of 115.5 L/m² d.

Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOP). UV/H₂O₂. Experiments were conducted using the same system for UV disinfection described above, dosing H₂O₂ in the recirculation tank at the start of the test. The doses of H₂O₂ tested were 20 mg/L and 40 mg/L.

Figure 1. a) 40W low-pressure lamp; b) GAC column; c) CW at mesocosm scale.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For stormwater, rainwater and greywater, there is no specific regulatory framework on the treatment to be applied or the quality objectives to be achieved for subsequent reuse. However, the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2006) established guidelines for greywater treatment, recognising firstly the need for biological treatment to remove COD and suspended solids, and a further disinfection for its reuse as service water. In the case of wastewater, the urban wastewater treatment directive (UWWTD, 2024) indicates the nutrient limits (N and P) to be respected for agglomerations of populations equivalent (PE) <150 000 and the need for a quaternary treatment to remove MP when PE >150 000. There are several solutions for this purification step, from separation processes such as adsorption or membranes to AOPs and ozone, both capable of simultaneously eliminating MP and pathogenic bacteria present in the effluent. After the deep analysis of the scientific literature, European regulation and guidelines of the different international organizations, the most appropriate treatments according to the type of water and the most suitable application for each of them were identified (Table 1).

According to the previous research, a set of 15 experiments was proposed to be developed with real effluents collected in Luxembourg, applying the proposed technologies and tested under several operational conditions. These results will be useful to find the relationships between water characteristics, the boundary of the technology and the water quality to be achieved for a safe reuse, which could be extrapolated to other areas.

Table 1. Summary of the findings from an extensive literature review (27 European, International and National regulations; more than 100 scientific publications)

Alternative source* of water	Recommended treatment	Preferred application
Stormwater and rainwater	Natural based solution (UWWTD, 2024) Disinfection	Service water Irrigation of landscapes
Greywater	Prefiltration Biological treatment (or membrane) Disinfection (Van de Walle, <i>et al.</i> 2023)	Service water Irrigation of landscapes
Wastewater	WWTP with downstream technology <ul style="list-style-type: none">• <150 000 PE – UV disinfection• >150 000 PE – AOP/O₃ + by products removal (Rizzo <i>et al.</i> 2020)	Irrigation of crops

*Water that can be safely reused after the appropriate treatment to reach the required quality standards

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the Fonds National de la Recherche (FNR) of Luxembourg for supporting the project LëtZREUSE (18120744) in the frame of the Industrial Fellowship Program. The authors are especially thankful to our project partner TR-Engineering for its collaboration.

REFERENCES

World Health Organization. (2006). *Overview of greywater management Health considerations* (No. WHO-EM/CEH/125/E)

Directive of the European Parliament and of The Council of 27 November 2024 concerning urban wastewater treatment (UWWTD)

Van de Walle, A., Kim, M., Alam, M. K., Wang, X., Wu, D., Dash, S. R., Rabaey, K., Kim, J. (2023). Greywater reuse as a key enabler for improving urban wastewater management. *Environmental science and ecotechnology*, **16**, 100277.

Rizzo, L., Gernjak, W., Krzeminski, P., Malato, S., McArdell, C. S., Sanchez Perez, J. A., Schaar, H., Fatta-Kassinos, D. (2020). Best available technologies and treatment trains to address current challenges in urban wastewater reuse for irrigation of crops in EU countries. *Science of the Total Environment*, **710**, 136312.